

What do Mobile Gamers Want? A Study to Increase Mobile Gamers Loyalty and In-App Purchase Intention Using Perceived Value Multidimensional Model.

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Abstract. There's been an exploding population of gamers in Southeast Asia since the covid started. Most active players in Indonesia are at the age of 16 – 24, which means Gen Z is the most active group of players. The most popular genre to be played in mobile is MOBA games, MOBA games are a multiplayer online battle arena, where players use their selection of character to fight the other team by completing objectives. The most popular MOBA game at this time is Mobile Legend: Bang – Bang. Indonesia has its own MOBA game called Lokapala, which is developed by Anantarupa Studio. The studio promises to bring more e-sport tournaments in the future. Their studio needs to increase their Loyalty towards players and incentivize players to purchase in-game items. Therefore, this study will look at how players perceive MOBA games, in order for game developers to understand their perspective. That is why Perceived Value is suggested for this study in order to understand how it will affect Loyalty and how it will affect In-App Purchase Intention. Based on the results, all dimensions of Perceived Value such as Emotional Value, Utilitarian Value, Hedonic Value, and Economic Value can positively impact Loyalty amongst players. Loyalty also shows to have positive and significant influence over In-App Purchase Intention. However, results show that Economic Value and Emotional Value do not have any significant influence towards loyalty and a low positive impact.

Keywords: Mobile Game, Marketing, MOBA, Perceived Value, In-App Purchase Intention.

1 Introduction

The gaming industry in Southeast Asia has one of the most promising growths in recent years because of COVID – 19. Since then, there has been an explosion of growth in 2020 for more than 46% increase (Inmobi, 2021). Because of this phenomenon, they permanently added or changed their habits to do gaming activities (Inmobi, 2021). According to a report written by Meltwater (2024), the most active players worldwide are the age of 16 – 24. Same goes for Indonesia player base Meltwater (2024). According to IDN Times (2024), the most popular genre to be played by Indonesia Gen Z is

Multiplayer Online Battle Arena (MOBA) and First Person Shooter (FPS) as the second most popular genre. MOBA, or multiplayer online battle arena is a genre of online real-time strategy video games in which two teams go head-to-head and with their chosen character their goal is to protect their home base and destroy the infrastructure of the opposing team's stronghold (Dictionary.com). As in 2024, the most popular MOBA game in Indonesia is Mobile Legend: Bang – Bang (Yonatan, A. Z., 2024). Indonesia has its own local MOBA game called Lokapala. Developed by Anantarupa Studios, Lokapala is the first esports game from Indonesia and Southeast Asia (Lokapala - Game Page, 2024). Anantarupa Studios promise to bring more esports tournaments in the future (Anantarupa Studio, 2023). Although comparing it to other MOBA games like Mobile Legend: Bang – Bang in the e-sport mobile games scene. It's no surprise that a more mature IP is far more superior. This proof to be to a high bar for Lokapala. And according to outdated data from 2023, lokapala has only a download of 271,000 (Rizti, F, 2024). It is clear that mobile legends are no match for lokapala. This begs a question, how does an organization maintain and grow their loyal fanbase, while pursuing positive income? This research will investigate how mobile gamers value MOBA games in general, using the concept of "Perceived Value." By acknowledging how they value such games, organizations can take that into account when they are forming their business strategy in order to maintain their loyalty, which leads to In-App Purchase Intention. Previous research has also investigated the significance of Perceived Value in different industry or even in the same industry but more specific, such as an article by Rusli, M.G & Margaretha Pink Berlianto (2025) Dilan, Sugito, & Khourouh (2023), Rusli & and Lestari, Nitisanjaya, & Yosef Budi Susanto (2023).

2 Literature Review

2.1 Perceived Value

Perceived Value is fundamental in understanding consumer behavior and decision-making. Perceived Value refers to a consumer's assessment of a product or service's usefulness based on consumers' perceptions from what is obtained or offered (Rusli, M. G., & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). Several studies support this idea, because it helps to achieve customer thinking (Ha and Jang, 2010; Jensen, 1996 as cited by Rusli, M. G., & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). In marketing literature is common to use Hedonic Value and Utilitarian Value is often used (Ha and Jang, 2010), however two dimensions may be insufficient. Therefore, an additional dimension is added mainly Economic, and Emotional—to better capture it (Ha & Jang, 2010; Ray et al., 2012; Lu & Hsiao, 2010, as cited by Rusli & Berlianto, 2025).

Emotional Value.

Emotional Value plays an essential role in shaping consumer behavior in modern markets. Emotional Value refers to the utility derived from the level of feeling or affection when using a product or service (Lu & Hsiao, 2010; Sweeney and Soutar, 2001 as cited by Dilan, Sugito, & Khourouh, 2023). Consumers who practice rational consumption are

now starting to shift their purchase consumption to fulfill their psychological needs (Rusli & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). Dodds et al. (1991) argues that Emotional Value has a positive influence on purchase intention. This statement is further supported by several studies such as (Hsiao & Chen, 2016 as cited by Rusli & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). Another research suggests that Emotional Value has a positive impact on Satisfaction and Loyalty, which also positively affects In-App Purchase Intention (Rusli, M. G., & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025), because of this a hypothesis is made:

H1. Emotional Value has significant influence on Loyalty.

Utilitarian Value

Utilitarian value is related to the goal or specific task of a product or service (Ha & Jang, 2010 as cited by Rusli & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). It is defined as a comprehensive assessment of a functioning product or service, leading to satisfaction or disappointment according to the results of the task (Overby and Lee, 2006 as cited by Rusli & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). This value consists of three dimensions: efficiency, task specific and economical aspect (Ha & Jang, 2010). Studies show that Utilitarian Value has a positive impact towards Loyalty, because it initiates favorable intentions. (Jones et al., 2006 as cited by: Chuang, 2020), because of that a hypothesis is made:

H2. Utilitarian value has significant influence on Loyalty.

Economic Value

Economic Value is the direct value of a product or service to the level of quality and complexity of the provided feature (Ray et al., 2012; Verhoef, 2003; as cited by Chuang, 2020). Although it has traditionally been central to consumer decision making, its importance has declined as other value dimensions gain relevance (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Alford & Biswas, 2002, as cited by Rusli & Berlianto, 2025). Economic value consists of three dimensions: Price, Quality, and Benefits. Studies have shown that Economic Value has a significant and positive impact on customer Loyalty (Rusli, M. G., & Berlianto, 2025; Chuang, 2020). Therefore, a hypothesis can be made:

H3. Economic Value has significant influence on Loyalty.

Hedonic Value

The customer's detailed evaluation of profit and loss, such as entertainment and escape, is referred to as Hedonic Value (Overby & Lee, 2006, as cited by Rusli & Berlianto, 2025). "Perceived Hedonic Value" refers to the uniqueness, meaning and emotional arousal from an object or experience (Ha & Jang, 2010; Spangenberg et al., 1997, as cited by Rusli & Berlianto, 2025). A pleasant experience will result in a better level of satisfaction with customers (Avcilar & Ozsoy, 2015; Hanzae & Porgham, 2013; as cited by Rusli & Berlianto, 2025). Jones et al. (2006) suggest that Hedonic Value has positive effect on Loyalty. Therefore, a hypothesis is made:

H4. Hedonic Value has significant influence on Loyalty.

2.2 Loyalty

Loyalty is one of the most significant variables to influence purchase intentions (Lu et al.; Oliver, 2010/2014 as cited by Rusli & Berlianto, 2025). According to Dick and Basu (1994) as cited by (Rusli & Berlianto, 2025), Loyalty is a combination of patronage and attitude towards an entity, whether it is a brand, service, store, or vendor. In an online context, Loyalty is an important measurement to maintain in order to maintain return visits (Sohn & Lee, 2011). Loyalty towards a certain mobile game, describe as players inclination to continue to play or recommend that mobile game (Hsiao & Chen, 2016, as cited by Lestari, Nitisanjaya, & Susanto, 2023). Loyalty is a significant factor for In-App Purchase Intentions, the longer consumers spend time on the application, the more likely purchase intention to grow (Hsu & Lin, 2015; Rusli & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). Study suggests that Loyalty can be measured by how much consumers have preference and strong emotional attachments to certain products or services (Rusli & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025), therefore a hypothesis is made as follows:

H5. Loyalty has a positive has significant influence on In-App Purchase Intentions.

2.3 In – App Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is when a customer consciously making decisions to purchase a certain item or service (Lin, 2015, as cited by Rusli & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). In-App Purchase Intentions involves when consumers consciously think of buying digital items such as virtual goods and remove ads within a mobile application. Loyalty can significantly factor In-App Purchase Intentions (Hsu & Lin, 2015; Rusli & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). A study conducted by Widodo & Balqiah (2020) and Purnami & Agus, (2020) confirmed that there is a positive influence stimulating In-App Purchase within players.

3 Method

The population of this research is Indonesia Gen Z's, who played any MOBA games on their phone. This research uses quantitative methods, which require numerical data and statistical analysis; therefore a 5-Point Likert scale is used to collect data from MOBA players.

To calculate the findings, the Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) is chosen to calculate the findings by using smart-pls software. The reason is because this research has a fairly small sample size, and to accommodate more complex model structures with indicators (Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & G. Kuppelwieser, 2014).

All indicators were taken from Rusli, M.G & Margaretha Pink Berlianto (2025) studies and an additional indicator that is borrowed from Sweeney, J. C., & Soutar, G. (2001) studies. In total there are 5 Hedonic Value indicators (Rusli, M.G & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025) , 4 Utilitarian Value (Rusli, M.G & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025), 6 Emotional Value (Rusli, M.G & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025; Sweeney and Soutar, 2001) 4 Economic Value (Rusli, M.G & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025)

, 6 Loyal indicators (Rusli, M.G & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025) , and 4 In-App Purchase Intention indicators (Rusli, M.G & Margaretha Pink Berlianto, 2025). The purpose of the outer model is to check the validity and reliability of the measurement model that is used, using PLS-SEM to calculate it (Wong, 2013) The recommended threshold for the outer loading results is 0.7 (Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & G. Kuppelwieser, 2014). Because of that, indicators such as: Utilitarian Value 1, Economic Value 2, Emotional Value 6, Hedonic Value 2 are removed due to the fact that the indicators do not reach the threshold in the outer loading results.

A specific location is required to control the quality of the data. That is why cities like Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi are chosen (JABODETABEK).

The survey is distributed to several E-sport campuses around the chosen cities, as well as students of Binus Alam Sutera Campus via online chat. Asking volunteers on-site to fill in the survey has also been done. In total 289 respondents are gathered and only 202 are met.

The majority of respondents are male with $n = 155$ in total, compared to women with $n = 47$. The majority of respondents are students ($n = 171$), followed by working professionals ($n = 28$), freelancers ($n = 2$), and one entrepreneur ($n = 1$). In terms of locations, most respondents are from Tangerang ($n = 112$), followed by Jakarta ($n = 73$). Smaller groups come from Bekasi ($n = 8$) and Bogor ($n = 8$), while only one respondent each is from Depok. In terms of occupation, the majority of respondents are students ($n = 172$), followed by employed workers ($n = 28$). Only a few are freelancers ($n = 2$) and entrepreneurs ($n = 1$). In terms of monthly expenditure, the majority of respondents ($n = 80$) reportedly spent less than Rp 350,000. Which is considered to be low expense in Indonesia. This is followed by 53 respondents who spend Rp 1.2 million to Rp 6 million, 37 respondents reportedly spending Rp 530,000 to Rp 1.2 million, and 27 respondents in the Rp 350,000 to Rp 530,000 range. A smaller number of respondents indicated spending more than Rp 6 million ($n = 5$).

Despite the majority spending below Rp 350,000, 176 of them have made In-App Purchases in MOBA games before. When asked how frequently they purchase, using the 5-point likert scale, the result shows that the average value is 2.3. Value 1 indicates “Very Rarely” and value 5 indicates “Very Often”.

3.1 Validity and Reliability Test

Table 1. Construct Reliability and Validity

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	AVE
Eco. Value	0.811	0.815	0.888	0.725
Emo. Value	0.814	0.818	0.871	0.575
Hdnc. Value	0.808	0.809	0.874	0.634
Loyalty	0.905	0.909	0.927	0.679
In-app Prchs. Int.	0.875	0.855	0.914	0.726
Util. Val	0.707	0.702	0.836	0.630

As shown by table 1 above, all variables are valid and reliable with all AVE values ≥ 0.5 and Cronbach's alpha, Composite Reliability value above 0.7, as recommended by (Hair, M. Hult, M. Ringle, & Marko, 2022; Hair, Jr, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Gudergan, 2024).

Table 2. Discriminant Validity – Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) / Multicollinearity Test (VIF)

Variables	Eco. Value	Emo. Value	Hedonic. Value	Loyalty	In-App Prchs. Int.
Eco. Value				... / 1.736	
Emo. Value	0.788			... / 2.690	
Hdonic Value	0.649	0.884		... / 2.106	
Loyalty	0.602	0.839	0.685		... / 1.000
In-App Prchs. Int.	0.668	0.577	0.571	0.692	
Util. Value	0.428	0.523	0.406	0.566 / 1.203	0.339

As shown by table 2 above, all HTMT values are ≤ 0.85 , meaning all variables are distinctive to one another. Therefore, all variables are usable. Table 2 above also shows the result of multicollinearity test, results indicate that all variables are not corelated, because VIF value is ≤ 3 (Hair, M. Hult, M. Ringle, & Marko, 2022; Hair, Jr, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Gudergan, 2024).

The value of the coefficient is from 0 to 1, the greater the value, the better estimation of the dependent variable. (Hair et al., 2017; Moore et al., 2018). According to the results, Loyalty has a 0.570 of R square adjusted value. That means that Economic Value, Emotional Value, Hedonic Value, and Utilitarian Value can influence “Loyalty” by 57%. The rest of the influence comes from other independent outside this study. Same goes for “In-App Purchase Intention”, the result from table 4 suggest that “Loyalty” can influence “In-App Purchase Intention” by 39.7%. The rest of the value comes from other independent outside of this study.

3.2 HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Table 3. Table captions should be placed above the tables.

Hypothesis	Original Sample	P-Value (≤ 0.05)	Results	Conclusion
[H1] EMO.V \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.062	0.337	Not Significant	Rejected
[H2] Util.V \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.513	0.000	Significant	Accepted
[H3] Eco.V \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.131	0.125	Not Significant	Rejected
[H4] Hdnc.V \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.630	0.000	Significant	Accepted
[H5] Loyalty \Rightarrow In-app Prchs. Int.	0.194	0.002	Significant	Accepted

P-value is used to analyze whether the hypothesis is accepted or not. Original sample indicates how the independent variable will affect dependent variables, whether it's positive or negative impact. As shown above in table 3, H1 and H3 are rejected, and

H2, H4, H5 is accepted because P-value is ≤ 0.05 (Hair, M. Hult, M. Ringle, & Marko, 2022; Hair, Jr, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Gudergan, 2024)

Discussion

Based on the results shown in table 3 above, H1 and H3 are rejected, due to the fact that the P-value is ≤ 0.05 . Therefore, it can be concluded that Emotional Value and Economic Value have no noteworthy influence on Loyalty. With that, the rest of the hypothesis is accepted (H2, H4 and H5). It can be concluded that Utilitarian Value, Hedonic Value can significantly influence Loyalty, and Loyalty can significantly influence In-App Purchase Intention.

Original sample indicates the negative and positive influence of independent variables to dependent variables. Based on the original sample shown on table 3, H1, H2, H3, and H4, it suggests that the variables can positively influence Loyalty. H5 suggests that Loyalty can positively influence In-App Purchase Intention. however Emotional Value and Economic Value (H1 & H3), cannot significantly influence Loyalty.

Hypothesis Support

- Results of H1 shown in table 3 are supported from previous study by Rusli, M. G., & Berlianto (2025) and Dilan, Sugito, & Khourouh, 2023. Which also indicates positive impact but no significancy.
- Results of H2 shown in table 3 are supported from previous study by Rusli, M. G., & Berlianto (2025) and Chuang (2020).
- Results of H3 shown in table 3 are supported from previous study by Rusli, M. G., & Berlianto (2025). The study also found that Economic Value has no significancy.
- Results of H4 shown in table 3 are supported from previous study by Chuang (2020).
- Results of H5 shown in table 3 are supported from previous study by Chuang (2020), Rusli, M. G., & Berlianto (2025), Dilan, Sugito, & Khourouh, 2023, and Lestari, Niti-sanjaya, & Yosef Budi Susanto, 2023. Once again proving that Loyalty is a reliable indicator of Purchase Intention (Lu et al., 2015; Oliver, 2010 as cited by Rusli, M. G., & Berlianto, 2025).

4 CONCLUSION

Based on the result of this study, we can conclude that players who play MOBA games on their mobile pays attention to experience. Economic value and Emotional Value do have positive impact; however, it does not have any impact. Therefore, it is recommended that game developers enhance players' experience in order to increase Loyalty, rather than focusing on offering better virtual items or promoting about the game itself, it is much more meaningful for players to have a better experience while gaming. It is also wise to enhance the application experience and fix bug issues because players also pay attention to Utilitarian Value, which refers to how applications run their task.

Other than that, this study will also help other researchers in advancing their study about Perceived Value and Loyalty.

This study has limitations however, because this study mainly focuses on gaming industry with specific genre, every genre has its own type of consumer which may produce different results. For further research, a different genre of games with a broader scope of analysis is recommended, one example is to use satisfaction. Lastly a study on women player base can be considered as gaming are dominantly male and it proves to study about women in the gaming sphere.

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